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STRATEGIC PLANNING OF THE ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE OF THE ENTERPRISE

СТРАТЕГІЧНЕ ПЛАНУВАННЯ ОРГАНІЗАЦІЙНОЇ СТРУКТУРИ ПІДПРИЄМСТВА

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У статті розглянуті різні точки зору вчених щодо визначення понять «організаційна структура», «адаптація», «стратегічне планування». Виявлено роль стратегічного планування в діяльності підприємства. Досліджено основні напрями вдосконалення стратегічного планування на підприємстві. Запропоновано до використання схему здійснення адаптації організаційної структури в рамках стратегічного планування на підприємстві. Визначено необхідність проведення адаптації організаційної структури підприємства, що сприяє прискореному вирішенню управлінських завдань в рамках стратегічного планування. Запропоновано використання схеми процесу стратегічного планування, що включає адаптацію організаційної структури до вимог стратегії розвитку. Використання запропонованої схеми процесу стратегічного планування на підприємстві дозволить сформувати гнучку адаптивну організаційну структуру, що відповідає вимогам розробленої стратегії розвитку.

Ключові слова: організаційна структура, адаптація, адаптованість, адаптивна система, стратегічне планування, стратегія розвитку

Voskoboeva E.V., Romashchenko O.S. Strategic planning of the organizational structure of the enterprise. Scientific and methodical article.

The article discusses different points of view of scientists regarding the definition of the concepts of "organizational structure", "adaptation", "strategic planning". The role of strategic planning in the activities of the enterprise is revealed. The main directions of improving the strategic planning at the enterprise are investigated. A scheme for implementing the adaptation of the organizational structure within the framework of strategic planning at the enterprise is proposed for use. The necessity of adapting the organizational structure of the enterprise, contributing to the accelerated solution of management tasks within the framework of strategic planning, has been determined. It is proposed to use the scheme of the strategic planning process, including the adaptation of the organizational structure to the requirements of the development strategy.

The use of the proposed scheme of the strategic planning process at the enterprise will make it possible to form a flexible adaptive organizational structure that meets the requirements of the developed development strategy.

Keywords: organizational structure, adaptation, adaptability, adaptive system, strategic planning, development strategy

The modern stage of management for many enterprises is characterized by the search for new strategic areas of activity, the implementation of which will help to increase competitiveness. In these conditions, the formation of a new strategy necessarily requires adjustments to the management process and organizational structure of the enterprise, and also stimulates the search for new necessary resources and competencies. Management has a responsibility to determine to what extent the existing organizational structure is in line with a particular strategy and, if necessary, make appropriate changes.

Analysis of recent researches and publications

The work of such foreign and domestic scientists as A. Chandler, P. Drucker, G. Hall [1], L.I. Skubitskaya, I. Prodius, I. Soloviev and others. The work of such authors as A.A. Thompson, Z.E. Shershneva, S.V. Oborskaya [2], A.N. Sumets, M.I. Bondarenko [3].

Unsolved aspects of the problem

Despite a large number of scientific works that are devoted to the relationship between the strategy of an enterprise and its organizational structure, as well as the use of modern types of organizational management structures and their optimization, some aspects still remain unexplored. Therefore, the issue of the problem of adapting the organizational structure in the implementation of strategic planning requires a more detailed study.

The aim of the article is to substantiate the creation of an adaptive organizational structure of an enterprise in the implementation of strategic planning. In the process of the research, the methods of theoretical generalization and comparison were used (when defining the concepts of "organizational structure", "adaptation", "strategic planning"), system analysis (when determining the relationship between the adaptation of the organizational structure and the process of strategic planning), abstract-logical analysis (when summarizing the results, formulating conclusions).

The main part

The statement "strategy determines the structure", formulated by A. Chandler, requires managers to revise and adapt the organizational structure of the enterprise in accordance with the chosen development strategy.

The effectiveness of sustainable development management of an enterprise largely depends on the organizational structure used in this case, which is considered as a set of elements of the organization and the links between them.

According to S.A. Petrenko, the organizational structure is a set of production links and ordered flows of resources in the production system, as well as governing bodies and their definite relationship, which ensure the achievement of the strategic goals of the enterprise [4].

Let's define the content and features of the concept of "adaptation". In a broad sense, "adaptation of the enterprise" is the adaptation of the enterprise to changes in the external environment [5].

In the economic encyclopedia, adaptation (English adaptation, from Latin *adapto* – I adapt) is interpreted as the adaptation of the economic system and its individual subjects to the conditions of the changing external environment, production, labor, exchange, and the vital needs of the population [6]. The concept of adaptation in control theory overwhelmingly coincides with the concept of biology. From the point of view of biology, adaptation is an adaptation in the process of evolution of the structure, functions, behavior of organisms to certain conditions of existence (new or changed) [5].

An adaptive system is defined as "a system that can adapt to changes in internal and external conditions. If the actions of the external environment change in an unpredictable way, then changes in the characteristics of the controlled object also occur in an unpredictable way" [7].

The term "enterprise adaptation" is used both to define a process and an outcome. However, there is the concept of "adaptability", which reflects the result of the process. S.A. Kravchenko interprets adaptation as a change in the behavior of an enterprise in market conditions without changing the organization of the internal environment. N.V. Beloshkurskaya defines adaptation as the process of adaptation of an enterprise and its activities to the external environment, as well as the effective use of its production potential [8]. Such scientists as L.E. Dovgan and G.A. Mokhonko, consider adaptation from the point of view of strategic sustainability and define it as one of the main tools for achieving the ultimate goal [9].

The process of adaptive strategic planning is an integrated system of justification, adapted to the peculiarities of the external environment and internal capabilities of the object, strategic management models that form the basis for the implementation of the established strategic goals and development directions on the way of achieving the target state and position in the market by the enterprise. The product of adaptive strategic planning is strategy.

There are many definitions of the concept of "strategic planning". So, A.A. Thompson argues that strategic planning is a planned work that includes the development of forecasts, programs and plans that provide goals and strategies for the behavior of control objects in the future, allowing these objects to function effectively and quickly adapt to changes in environmental conditions. The need to revise the essence and content of measures in strategic planning for their use based on continuous monitoring and evaluation taking place outside and inside the enterprise is highlighted by Z.E. Shershnev and S.V. Oborskaya. The process of strategic planning is considered most fully in the work of A.N. Sumets, M.I. Bondarenko, who define strategic planning as a type of management activity associated with the development of strategies based on a set of actions and management decisions aimed at achieving the goals of the enterprise. This interpretation confirms the need to develop and form a strategic set at an enterprise as a real management tool.

A functional approach to enterprise management allows us to assert that planning is the basis for the effective implementation of such management functions as organization, motivation and control. It is on the basis of plans that tasks are determined and the interaction of specific performers is carried out. Thus, the planning process should not end with the development of plans for individual business processes and structural divisions (management levels) of the enterprise. An obligatory component of the system of plans of the enterprise should be planned tasks for individual performers.

To ensure the effectiveness of the process of adaptation to changing environmental conditions at the enterprise, it is necessary to create a strategic planning system. This system in industrial enterprises should be considered as a complex consisting of several subsystems (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Strategic planning system

Source: authors' own development

In addition to the main elements, including the system of plans, the process of strategic planning, the organizational structure of its management, the subsystem of information and organizational support, decision-making, it should be highlighted in its composition a subsystem of staffing, since the achievement of the goals of the enterprise depends on the qualifications of personnel, their strategic skills and knowledge. The study of the generalized characteristics of the elements of the strategic planning system allows us to identify the main directions of organizational actions for its improvement at industrial enterprises:

- improving the organizational structure aimed at implementing the strategy and ensuring the continuity of the planning process;
- creation of a system of information and analytical support for strategic planning;
- improvement of personnel processes in order to attract, develop and retain qualified and strategically oriented employees for the development and implementation of the company's strategy.

Allocation of the processes of strategic, current and operational management of the enterprise leads to the fact that the logic, content and methods of strategic, current and operational planning differ significantly.

Strategic planning is designed to solve three problems:

- satisfaction of the long-term interests of the participants in the activity of the enterprise, first of all, its owners and labor collective;
- coordination of the proposed results of the enterprise with the possible cost of resources;
- rational use of resources at the disposal of the enterprise.

The solution of the first of them requires the development of the enterprise (development of new markets, the release of new types of products, the introduction of new equipment and technologies, updating the resource base), that is, actions of a strategic nature, the development of which is the subject of strategic planning.

When developing a strategic plan, it is necessary, first of all, to determine the mission, goals and conditions of the enterprise for the future, based on the interests of the groups taking part in its activities; after that, develop a program of its activities for the future, as well as projects for the development of individual business processes of the enterprise.

The purpose of strategic planning is to plan the economic activities of the enterprise for the near and distant periods in accordance with the needs of the market and the possibilities of obtaining the necessary resources.

When planning the operational management process, it is necessary to note with whom the new business should be created and how it is planned to establish work with it. Requirements for the specialists that are necessary for the successful conduct of the business must be determined. The existing structure of the organization should facilitate the implementation of the strategy - if it does not correspond to this, then it must be adjusted, adapted to strategic changes. First of all, structural changes concern the management system: the principles and mechanisms of decision-making, the passage of information, planning, the system of motivation and material incentives. Such changes in the management system may also affect the formal structure (positions, subordination, change in the type of structure). Feedback is information about how the structure matches the organization's strategy. It can be expressed in economic and non-economic indicators.

It is important for the leaders of the organization to correctly recognize the direction of the factor being influenced and to take appropriate measures: it is necessary to harmonize the organizational structure of the units involved in the business process, the system of interaction of all services, coordination and control of their activities (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Diagram of the strategic planning process

Source: authors' own development

Distinctive features of the strategic plan are long-term indicative nature and the use of generalized probabilistic information. Its development is about identifying and solving unstructured and insufficiently structured problems.

It is advisable to solve the second task in the course of current planning, and the third - in operational planning.

A. Gridzhuk schematically distinguished long-, short-term and operational planning according to the levels of the organizational structure [10].

The task of top management (long-term planning) is to make the process of forming a strategy accessible and understandable for employees of the organization, to facilitate their maximum involvement in developing a strategy, since its understanding by employees affects the final result. Consequently, the management determines the general goal of the enterprise and the main ways to achieve it. The preparation of mid-term plans is delegated to the heads of departments and chief specialists in the field. The duties of specialists also include analysis of the internal and external environment of the enterprise, making forecasts and scenarios for the development of events. The lower-level executives are in charge of formulating short-term operational goals and plans.

The adaptation of the organizational structure is designed to ensure:

- aligning the organizational structure with goals and strategy; – the distribution of functions and powers, which allows management to focus on development issues, rather than on current operational problems;
- no duplication of functions;
- effective connection of blocks.

The adaptation of the organizational structure of the enterprise includes the following stages of work:

- formalization of management processes (formation of regulatory documents, determination of a set of key competencies and officials of management bodies);
- designing a new organizational structure (diagnostics, developing an organizational structure based on target indicators and the structure of business processes, ensuring a balance of functions) [11].

The adaptation of the organizational structure of the enterprise allows to achieve: orientation of the enterprise to the most important strategic goals; improved maneuverability; improving the speed and quality of individual jobs such as customer service, reporting, financial analysis, etc.

Adaptation of the organizational structure of a business entity is aimed at creating new, reorganizing or reducing existing enterprise subsystems, taking into account strategic planning. The result of adaptation of this level is the formation of a flexible organizational structure, which is characterized by the ability to accelerate the solution of management tasks, the ability to respond to changes in strategy.

Conclusions

The current state of the economy is characterized by an active search for directions to improve the efficiency of the enterprise and its competitiveness. It is the purposeful strategic planning of the management process that makes it possible to determine not only the level of achieving the efficiency of the enterprise, but also the possibilities for its improvement and development.

The development of a new strategy becomes the primary reason for adapting the organizational structure of the enterprise to its conditions and making adjustments to the management process. Based on the results of adaptation, a flexible organizational structure is designed, which makes it possible to most effectively implement the strategy developed in the process of strategic planning.

Thus, the adaptation of the organizational structure of the enterprise, contributing to the accelerated solution of management problems, is an integral element of strategic planning. Further research in this direction consists in developing scientific and methodological approaches to adapting the organizational structure of an enterprise to the conditions of the external environment.

Abstract

The article discusses different points of view of scientists regarding the definition of the concepts of "organizational structure", "adaptation", "strategic planning". The role of strategic planning in the activities of the enterprise is revealed. The main directions of improving the strategic planning at the enterprise are investigated. A scheme for implementing the adaptation of the organizational structure within the framework of strategic planning at the enterprise is proposed for use. The necessity of adapting the organizational structure of the enterprise, contributing to the accelerated solution of management tasks within the framework of strategic planning, has been determined. It is proposed to use the scheme of the strategic planning process, including the adaptation of the organizational structure to the requirements of the development strategy.

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Allocation of processes of strategic, current and operational management of the enterprise leads to the fact that the logic, content and methods of strategic, current and operational planning differ significantly. The adaptation of the organizational structure of the enterprise allows to achieve: orientation of the enterprise to the most important strategic goals; improved maneuverability; improving the speed and quality of individual jobs such as customer service, reporting, financial analysis, etc. It is the purposeful strategic planning of the management process that makes it possible to determine not only the level of achieving the efficiency of the enterprise, but also the possibilities for its improvement and development.

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